

Study of the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of the alkoxide decomposition of 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide in dioxane-ethanol mixtures

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The third order rate constants of the reaction between 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide and sodium ethoxide in binary dioxane-ethanol mixtures have been determined as a function of temperature. The reaction is accelerated largely upon substitution of most of the ethanol in the medium by the non-polar dioxane solvent. The observed activation energy decreases progressively with increasing dioxane concentration and such decrease may be due to the relative changes of solvation of the reactants and the activated complex.

The thermodynamic parameters ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger decrease over the range 10–50% (v/v) dioxane. The determined isokinetic temperature (β) indicates that the reaction is enthalpy - controlled.

Effects of solvent structure on the rates of alkoxide decomposition of phosphonium salts have been the subject of our interest¹. The nature of the attacking ion in substitution reactions, specially in protic solvent, is known to exert pronounced effects on rates and mechanisms, particularly if the interactions are of the ion-ion type². The alkaline decomposition of phosphonium salts is one of the best known nucleophilic displacement reactions at phosphorus. Although early kinetic and stereochemical studies³ clarified many of the details of the mechanism of this type of reaction, it is believed that the alkoxide promoted decomposition of 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide in non-aqueous dioxane-ethanol mixtures in which the nucleophile is ethoxide anion, proceeds via a hexacovalent intermediate². The overall reactions are as follows :

For this purpose kinetic and thermodynamic study involving the decomposition of 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide in a series of dioxane-ethanol mixtures in which the nucleophile is ethoxide anion, has been performed with special reference to the solvation states of the ions, which will definitely depend on the nature of the medium, and thus emphasize that the transition state solvation is controlling the reaction rate. These solvent systems

allow a continuous change from the polar, hydrogen-bonding character of ethanol to the solvent characteristics of the non-polar dioxane. The basic nucleophiles may be expected to become highly reactive in aprotic dioxane owing to the lack of hydrogen bond stabilization⁴.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants for the reaction in ethanol-dioxane mixture at various temperatures have been determined (Table 1). The linearity of kinetic plots from which these rate constants are calculated indicates a third order behaviour for the reaction, i.e. first order dependence on the concentration of the phosphonium cation and second order on the concentration of the ethoxide ions⁵.

Table 1. Observed rate constants and energies for the alkaline decomposition of 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide in dioxane-ethanol mixtures at different temperatures

Dioxane content v/v%	K' (dm ⁶ mol ⁻²)				E kJ mol ⁻¹
	15 ^o	20 ^o	25 ^o	30 ^o	
10	16.76	27.08	42.50	67.50	67.19
20	77.51	113.72	166.67	238.33	54.45
30	216.67	289.63	377.43	577.89	48.73
40	1153.05	1520.02	2003.77	2641.49	40.07
50	2641.49	3482.16	5270.46	6336.49	30.75

The observed activation energy (E) decreases as the dioxane component in the solvent mixture is increased. Thus, the value of E which amounts to 67.18 kJ mol⁻¹ in 10% dioxane, drops to as low a value as 30.75 kJ mol⁻¹ in 50% (v/v) dioxane-EtOH mixtures (Table 1). The drop follows a least-square correlation of the activation energy with the solvent composition in the form, $E = 67.19$ [dioxane] vol % kJ mol⁻¹, corr coeff. = 0.999.

Generally, the activation energy decreases progressively with increasing dioxane content. The main contribution to the decrease in E is due to the first step of the reaction, involving the formation of a neutral hexacovalent intermediate in the OEt^- reactions². The increase in solvation of the phosphorane intermediate as well as the decrease in solvation of ethoxide anions both help in the decrease of the activation energy.

According to the previous workers⁶, the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents attached to phosphorus in a phosphonium salt would be expected to accelerate the hydrolysis reaction⁷. This was discussed on the basis of the theory of inductive and mesomeric effects and on the presumption that the reaction involves a nucleophilic attack of the ethoxide ion on the phosphorus atom which is carrying a small positive charge. It is expected, therefore, that the introduction of a 3-bromopropyl instead of a phenyl group will act with its larger $-I$ effect to increase the positive charge on phosphorus and thereby increase the availability of its d -orbitals, i.e. making them less diffuse and hence more suitable for bonding during the formation of the hexacovalent intermediate⁸. In other words, it can be concluded that in the alkaline hydrolysis of phosphonium salts, the inductive effects of the substituents and the stability of the leaving group are of major importance in accelerating the rate of the reaction.

Fig. 1. Variation of $\log k$ with the concentration of organic solvent for the EtO^- reaction in dioxane-EtOH mixtures

Consequently, the plot of $\log K'$ against $\log [\text{dioxane}]$ should be linear. Such plots gave a linear relationship in the high range of dioxane content, where the transition complex is expected to be almost entirely solvated by dioxane. The slope of the linear part is 5 which is indicative of a large number of solvent molecules in the solvation sheath. On the other hand, in the range of high EtOH content, the plot of $\log k$ against $\log [\text{EtOH}]$ (Fig. 1) gave a straight-line with a negative slope indicating that the reactants (mainly the OEt^- anions) and not the transition state are almost entirely solvated by EtOH. This will lead to a considerable lowering of potential energy of the reactants only and a consequent large increase in the over all activation energy⁹ as is actually obtained

Further study of solvent effects can also be obtained from calculation of the thermodynamic parameters of the activated complex. The values of these functions, calculated at 25° for the reaction in dioxane-EtOH mixtures are listed in Table 2. The changes of these parameters are indicative of the internal structural changes of the medium and their influence on the reaction rate. ΔG^\ddagger decreases smoothly with increasing dioxane concentration, where the phenomenon of desolvation is encountered. This is evident from Table 2, and which also shows that the changes in ΔG^\ddagger are reflected in a considerable decrease in ΔH^\ddagger . From the plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for the different dioxane mixtures, the isokinetic temperature (β) was estimated. For the hydrolysis reaction, the isokinetic temperature was 449 K which is too high with respect to the experimental temperature (298 K), indicating that the rate of the reaction should be enthalpy-controlled¹⁰.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of activation for the alkaline decomposition of 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide in dioxane-ethanol mixtures at 298.15 K

Dioxane v/v %	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}
10	63.69	-3.41	64.71
20	60.31	27.99	51.97
30	58.25	40.27	46.25
40	54.12	55.46	37.59
50	51.72	78.69	28.27

The observation that the activation entropy decreases is attributed to solvation of the activated complex to a less extent than that of the reactants. The incorporation of solvent into the transition state entails a loss of entropy. This behaviour indicates specific solvation¹¹ and hence a non-random distribution of the solvent molecules. The large drop in ΔG^\ddagger values reflects the decrease in free energy involved in breaking hydrogen bonds with the reactant anions, which will decrease by decreasing the ethanol content of the medium.

Experimental

Pure 3-bromopropyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (Fluka) was used. Ethanol was dried by refluxing over freshly obtained quick lime, and then fractionated; a middle fraction was collected over less than 0.05°. Dioxane was purified using standard methods¹². Water used was freshly distilled from alkaline potassium permanganate. Sodium ethoxide solution was prepared from sodium metal (B.D.H.) and ethanol.

Reaction rates were determined by following the decrease in concentration of ethoxide during the course of the reaction. In the reaction with alkoxides, the reaction vessel was stoppered to prevent moisture. The kinetic procedure was performed as described earlier¹³.

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